
A PRACTICAL APPROACH TO THE CALCULATION OF ELLIPTICAL PERIMETERS

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ABSTRACT

The calculation of elliptical perimeters is a long-standing problem in mathematics. The present paper describes an approach to the calculation of elliptical perimeters that stems from the effort to apply mathematics to a concrete engineering problem. The proposed solution is sufficiently generic to be of widespread use in a range of industrial applications.

1 Introduction

In mathematics, an ellipse is a plane curve that results from the intersection of a cone by a plane in a way that produces a closed curve. More formally, an ellipse is a plane curve surrounding two focal points, such that for all points on the curve, the sum of the two distances to the focal points is a constant. The mathematical analysis of ellipses is important, for objects with elliptical geometries can be found in almost every area of scientific enquiry. In astronomy, for example, the orbital paths of celestial objects often conforms to an elliptical geometry. Ellipses can also be found in disciplines that are directed to a more earthly realm. In dentistry, for example, the structure of the maxillary arch can be modelled as an ellipsoid, and the calculation of elliptical perimeters has proved to be of practical significance relative to aspects of orthodontic treatment [1].

Despite their seeming simplicity, ellipses have proved to be a challenging target for mathematical analysis. A particular problem relates to the calculation of an ellipse's perimeter (or circumference). While a simple algebraic solution exists for the calculation of an ellipse's area, there are only approximate solutions for the calculation of an ellipse's perimeter [2]. This has been a long-standing problem in mathematics—one whose historical pedigree can be traced back to at least the days of Kelper [3]. In attempting to derive a solution to the calculation of elliptical perimeters, mathematicians have explored a number of different approaches, many of which are rooted in techniques derived from differential geometry [4, 5]. While these techniques can be useful, they are often unwieldy in practice, and this has motivated the search for more concise solutions [6].

The present paper describes a novel approach to the calculation of elliptical perimeters that is rooted in elementary geometry. The proposed solution was developed as part of a large-scale civil engineering project involving the development of canals with elliptical cross sections. The success of the project required the derivation of a formula to calculate the perimeter of these cross sections in advance of the actual construction of the canals. The solution described below represents the outcome of efforts to solve this problem, using a combination of theoretical insight and empirical testing with 'toy' models of the relevant problem domain. This solution proved to be effective in respect of the aforementioned civilian infrastructure project. Beyond that, however, the solution has also proved to be effective in a number of other engineering contexts, including, for example, the construction of an air extraction system for automobile paint spray booths.

Figure 1: Geometric elements included for the purpose of calculating elliptical perimeters. The ellipse whose perimeter is to be calculated is denoted by the dashed line. Two circles are superimposed on the ellipse, with the smaller (inner) circle having a diameter equal to the ellipse’s smaller diameter ($2b$) and the larger (outer) circle having a diameter equal to the ellipse’s larger diameter ($2a$). These circles function as a form of ‘geometric scaffolding’ that supports the effort to derive a solution to the primary problem: the calculation of the ellipse’s perimeter. It should be noted that the lines OC and OD are perpendicular and $\sin 90^\circ = 1$.

2 Proposed Solution

In Figure 1, a represents the ellipse’s semi-major axis, which is half of the ellipse’s major axis. b , by contrast represents the ellipse’s semi-minor axis, which is half the ellipse’s minor axis. OAB is a sector corresponding to a quarter of the smaller (or inner) circle, which has a diameter of $2b$. ODC is a sector corresponding to a quarter of the larger (or outer) circle, which has a diameter of $2a$.

The sectors OAB and ODC correspond to the triangles $OA'B'$ and $OD'C'$ such that:

$$\begin{aligned} OA &= OA' \\ OB &= OB' \\ AB &= \overline{A'B'} \\ DC &= \overline{D'C'} \end{aligned}$$

Note that we are straightening the arcs AB and DC to give us the straight lines $\overline{A'B'}$ and $\overline{D'C'}$. The length of these lines is the same as the length of the two arcs: AB and DC . [The use of the overline notation (as in $\overline{A'B'}$) indicates the straight line equivalent of the corresponding arc (i.e., AB).]

We can calculate the length of $\overline{A'B'}$ and $\overline{D'C'}$ as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \overline{A'B'} &= AB = \frac{\pi}{2}b \\ \overline{D'C'} &= DC = \frac{\pi}{2}a \end{aligned}$$

We can now determine the lengths of the sides of the two triangles depicted in Figure 1 (i.e., $OA'B'$ and $OD'C'$). These lengths are as follows:

Figure 2: Simplified view of the triangular geometries depicted in Figure 1. The line $B'D'$ corresponds to the arc BD in Figure 1.

$$\begin{aligned} OA' &= OB' = b \\ \overline{A'B'} &= \frac{\pi}{2}b \\ OC' &= OD' = a \\ \overline{D'C'} &= \frac{\pi}{2}a \end{aligned}$$

A simplified view of the two triangles $OA'B'$ and $OD'C'$ depicted in Figure 1 is presented in Figure 2. Note that Figure 2 includes a line connecting B' and D' . This line is not represented in Figure 1. For the time being, we can treat $B'D'$ as a line that connects the points B' (on the perimeter of the inner circle) and point D' (on the perimeter of the outer circle). Later, it will be shown that this line ($B'D'$) corresponds to the straightened version of the arc BD in Figure 1. Given that the arc BD in Figure 1 is one quarter of the perimeter of the ellipse, then the same will be true of $B'D'$. Accordingly, by determining the length of $B'D'$ in Figure 2, we can calculate the perimeter of the ellipse in Figure 1.

Using trigonometry, it can be shown that $\angle OA'B' = \angle OB'A' = \angle OC'D' = \angle OD'C' = 38.2423^\circ$. Consider, for example, the triangle $OC'K'$ in Figure 2. The angle $\angle OC'K'$ can be calculated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} OC'^2 &= C'K'^2 + K'O^2 \\ OC' &= a \\ C'K' &= \frac{\pi}{4}a \\ a^2 &= \frac{\pi^2}{16}a^2 + K'O^2 \\ K'O &= a\sqrt{1 - \frac{\pi^2}{16}} \\ a \sin \angle OC'K' &= K'O = a\sqrt{1 - \frac{\pi^2}{16}} \end{aligned}$$

Therefore:

$$\begin{aligned} \angle OA'B' &= \angle OB'A' = \angle OC'D' = \angle OD'C' = 38.2423^\circ \\ \sin 38.2423^\circ &= \sqrt{1 - \frac{\pi^2}{16}} = 0.619 \end{aligned}$$

We can now calculate the angle $\angle C'OD'$ in Figure 2:

$$\angle C'OD' = 180^\circ - (2 \times 38.2423^\circ) = 103.5154^\circ$$

We know that the area of a quarter of the smaller circle in Figure 1 (i.e., the area of the sector OAB) is:

$$\text{Area } OAB = \frac{\pi b^2}{4}$$

The area of the triangle $OA'B'$ in Figure 2, which corresponds to the sector OAB in Figure 1, is:

$$\text{Area } OA'B' = \frac{\pi b^2}{4} 0.619$$

The area of a quarter of the larger circle in Figure 1 (i.e., the area of the sector ODC) is:

$$\text{Area } ODC = \frac{\pi a^2}{4}$$

The area of the triangle $OD'C'$ in Figure 2, which corresponds to the sector ODC in Figure 1, is:

$$\text{Area } OD'C' = \frac{\pi a^2}{4} 0.619$$

The region ADB in Figure 1 has the following area:

$$\text{Area } ADB = \frac{\pi}{4} ab - \frac{\pi}{4} b^2 = \frac{\pi}{4} b(a - b)$$

The area of the triangle $A'D'B'$ in Figure 2, which corresponds to the region ADB in Figure 1, is equal to:

$$B'M = (a - b) \sqrt{1 - \frac{\pi^2}{16}} = (a - b) \times 0.619$$

$$\text{Area } A'D'B' = \frac{\pi}{4} b(a - b) \times 0.619$$

The region DBC in Figure 1 has the following area:

$$\text{Area } DBC = \frac{\pi}{4} a^2 - \frac{\pi}{4} ab = \frac{\pi}{4} a(a - b)$$

And the area of the triangle $D'B'C'$ in Figure 2, which corresponds to the region DBC in Figure 1, is:

$$\text{Area } D'B'C' = \frac{\pi}{4} a(a - b) 0.619$$

The ratio of the areas of the regions ADB and DBC in Figure 1 is:

$$\frac{\text{Area } ADB}{\text{Area } DBC} = \frac{\frac{\pi}{4} b(a - b)}{\frac{\pi}{4} a(a - b)} = \frac{b}{a}$$

And the ratio of the areas of the triangles $A'D'B'$ and $D'B'C'$ in Figure 2, which correspond to the regions ADB and DBC in Figure 1, is:

$$\frac{\text{Area } A'D'B'}{\text{Area } D'B'C'} = \frac{\frac{\pi}{4} b(a - b) 0.619}{\frac{\pi}{4} a(a - b) 0.619} = \frac{b}{a}$$

In the above, $\frac{\pi}{4} ab$ is a quarter of the ellipse's area and $\frac{\pi}{4} a^2$ and $\frac{\pi}{4} b^2$ are a quarter of the areas of the two circles depicted in Figure 1. Therefore, the areas of OAB , ODC , ADB , and DBC in Figure 1 are $\frac{1}{0.619}$ times the areas of the corresponding triangles $OA'B'$, $OD'C'$, $A'D'B'$, and $D'B'C'$ in Figure 2. In addition, all the sides of the sectors and regions DBC , ADB , ODC , and OAB in Figure 1 (when these are opened up to straighten the arcs and thus form triangles) are equal to the sides of $D'B'C'$, $A'D'B'$, $OD'C'$, and $OA'B'$ in Figure 2.

To help us understand why DB (in Figure 1) is equal to $D'B'$ (in Figure 2), consider the circular trapezoid, $ADCB$, in Figure 1. (This circular trapezoid has been rotated 90° (counterclockwise) around the centre O .) Imagine that BC and AD are made of a rigid (inflexible) material and AB , DC , and BD are made of a pliable material (such as a soft, albeit

inelastic, thread). If we pull AD and BC away from each other, we will have an isosceles trapezoid, corresponding to the trapezoid $A'D'C'B'$ in Figure 2. In Figure 1, BD is the diagonal of our circular trapezoid, and it is also the common side between the regions BCD and ABD .

In effect, what we are doing here is straightening the arc BD in Figure 1, and we are doing this while restricting the motion of the points B and D in Figure 1 such that they remain on the perimeters of the smaller and larger circles, respectively. Point B will thus rotate (clockwise) to occupy the position of B' , while point D will rotate (counterclockwise) to occupy the position of D' .

We now have two possibilities:

1. $B'D' > BD$: If this is the case, then $B'D'$ cannot form a straight line. The result is that it cannot form the two triangles $D'B'C'$ and $D'B'A'$ in Figure 2.
2. $B'D' < BD$: If this is the case, then, given that the points B' and D' are required to lie on the perimeters of the smaller and larger circles, then the imaginary thread connecting the points B and D will be too short and will be forced to break as these points (B and D) are moved to the location of B' and D' . Accordingly, if $B'D' < BD$, the ratio of the areas of $A'D'B'$ and $D'B'C'$ cannot be $\frac{b}{a}$, as was specified above. In addition, the area coefficient of the triangles $A'D'B'$ and $D'B'C'$ (in Figure 2), relative to the corresponding regions ADB and DBC (in Figure 1), cannot be:

$$0.619 = \sqrt{1 - \frac{\pi^2}{16}} = \sin 38.2423^\circ$$

This is not possible given that:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\text{Area } ADB}{\text{Area } DBC} &= \frac{b}{a} \\ \frac{\text{Area } A'D'B'}{\text{Area } D'B'C'} &= \frac{\frac{\pi}{4}b(a-b)0.619}{\frac{\pi}{4}a(a-b)0.619} = \frac{b}{a} \\ \frac{\text{Area } A'D'B'}{\text{Area } ADB} &= \sqrt{1 - \frac{\pi^2}{16}} = 0.619 \\ \frac{\text{Area } D'B'C'}{\text{Area } DBC} &= \sqrt{1 - \frac{\pi^2}{16}} = 0.619 \end{aligned}$$

The upshot is that $D'B'$ must be equal to DB . This is because we have established that $D'B'$ cannot be larger or smaller than DB : the ratio of the areas of $A'D'B'$ and $D'B'C'$ in Figure 1, corresponding to the triangles ADB and DBC in Figure 2, cannot be 0.619, and the ratio of the triangles $A'D'B'$ and $D'B'C'$ in Figure 2, corresponding to the regions ADB and DBC in Figure 1, must be $\frac{b}{a}$. Therefore, BD must be equal to $B'D'$.

From Figure 1, we can see that the arc BD corresponds to one quarter of the ellipse's perimeter. We have also established that $BD = B'D'$. Accordingly, we can calculate the perimeter of the ellipse by determining the length of the line $B'D'$ in Figure 2. Given that $B'D'$ is the hypotenuse of the triangle $B'MD'$ in Figure 2, we can calculate the value of $B'D'$ as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} B'M^2 &= B'C'^2 - C'M^2 \\ B'C' &= (a - b) \\ C'M &= \frac{C'D' - A'B'}{2} = \frac{\frac{\pi}{2}a - \frac{\pi}{2}b}{2} = \frac{\frac{\pi}{2}(a - b)}{2} = \frac{\pi}{4}(a - b) \\ MD' &= C'D' - C'M \\ MD' &= \frac{\pi}{2}a - \frac{\pi}{4}a + \frac{\pi}{4}b = \frac{\pi}{4}(a + b) \\ B'M &= \sqrt{(a - b)^2 - \frac{\pi^2}{16}(a - b)^2} = (a - b)\sqrt{1 - \frac{\pi^2}{16}} = 0.619(a - b) \\ B'D'^2 &= (a - b)^2 - \frac{\pi^2}{16}(a - b)^2 + \frac{\pi^2}{16}(a + b)^2 = (a - b)^2 + \frac{\pi^2}{4}ab \\ B'D' &= BD = \sqrt{(a - b)^2 + \frac{\pi^2}{4}ab} \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, the ellipse's perimeter is given by the following formula:

$$4\sqrt{(a-b)^2 + \frac{\pi^2}{4}ab}$$

And if the ellipse's larger and smaller diameters are equal, then the formula will be equal to the circumference of a circle with the same diameter.

3 Conclusion

The present paper describes a practical approach to the calculation of elliptical perimeters, which was developed using a combination of theoretical insight and empirical testing with toy models. The approach involves the use of geometric elements that are superimposed on the target ellipse to support the derivation of potential solutions. In the present case, these geometric elements correspond to the two circles in Figure 1. Such elements function as a form of 'geometric scaffolding' that aids the process of mathematical reasoning. This establishes an interesting parallel with work in the cognitive science literature that seeks to show how the creation and manipulation of problem-relevant representations can help to support the search for candidate solutions [7, 8, 9].

The present solution was inspired by the need to resolve the mathematical challenges associated with a large-scale civilian infrastructure project, namely, the calculation of canal perimeters with elliptical geometries. The formula developed as part of this solution proved sufficient for the purposes of the construction effort, enabling us to calculate elliptical geometries in advance of the actual construction activities. The solution has also proved to be of great practical utility across a number of other projects, including the construction of an air extraction system for automobile paint spray booths. This suggests the solution may be widely applicable to a number of industrial projects and applications, helping to support the effort to calculate the properties of elliptical objects at a variety of spatial scales. I present this solution in the hope that it may support the practical effort to apply mathematics to engineering problems, as well as stimulate debates and discussions pertaining to the mathematical properties of elliptical geometries.

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